

Field determination of gas exchange with the tritium/helium-3 method

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As a result of atmospheric nuclear weapon testing, tritium (radioactive labelled water molecule, HTO, radioactive mean life 17.69 yrs) is present in continental lakes and in the world oceans. Radioactive decay of tritium into the stable isotope helium-3 causes super-saturation of this isotope in the water. This tritiogenic helium-3 excess is lost to the atmosphere by gas exchange (evasion).

There are two modes of field experiments, which are based on this fact, e.g., the steady-state (T. Torgersen, Z. Top, W.B. Clarke, W.J. Jenkins and W.S. Broecker, 1977) and the transient mode (W. Weiss, H. Leh, K.H. Fischer, W.B. Clarke, Z. Top, B. Kromer and W. Roether, 1978). In the steady-state mode it is assumed that the processes of radioactive decay of tritium, internal mixing of a lake or the ocean, and the evasion of tritiogenic helium-3 are in a steady-state, in which case the gas exchange rate at a given place can be estimated from a single depth-profile of tritium and helium-3. Gas exchange rates of 2-4 m/d have been estimated this way (T. Torgersen et al. 1977) (no wind data given).

The applicability of the transient mode is much more elaborate because it requires a time series of tritium and helium-3 profiles. The idea is that the flux density of the helium-3 evasion as a result of changes of external parameters, e.g. for example wind speed and the helium-3 concentration gradient across the air-sea interface, can be determined by a series of tritium and helium-3 depth-profiles. The gas exchange rate can be calculated from the experimental data. Results of such measurements are available

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for Lake Constance (W. Weiss et al.) and for the Western Mediterranean (W. Weiss and W. Jenkins, in preparation). Gas exchange rates of 3.5-5.6 and of 33 m/d have been obtained. The resp. mean wind speed (10 m height) was 5-7 and 17 m/sec. The experiments at Lake Constance are being continued and additional experiments are planned at Lake Geneva where periods of high wind speeds are not uncommon during winter time (S.W. Bauer and W.H. Graf, 1979).

The comparison between the helium-3 results and those obtained by experiments with other gases (Rn-222, CO₂, O₂ etc.), is by models (cf. B. Jähne and K.O. Münnich, this issue), which relate the differences in the gas exchange rate to differences of molecular properties (diffusivity, Schmidt number, cf. B. Jähne and K.O. Münnich, this issue) of the gases.

The limited helium-3 gas exchange data available so far indicate that the wind dependence is probably much more pronounced than hitherto expected (T.H. Peng, W.S. Broecker, G.G. Mathieu, Y.-H. Li, 1979). As on the other hand the absolute value of the helium-3 gas exchange rate obtained at 17 m/sec wind speed (if corrected for differences in diffusivity) favourably agrees with results of wind tunnel experiments reported during this symposium (H.C. Broecker, this issue), it is concluded that a strong dependence of the gas exchange rate on wind speed exists in nature. The actual relationship between gas exchange rate and wind speed under natural conditions cannot be derived from field data at the present time (cf. also B. Kromer and W. Roether, this issue). In laboratory experiments bilinear, trilinear and even quadratic functions have been observed (H.C. Broecker, this issue, and B. Jähne et al., 1979).

There is a constraint to the applicability of any such relationship to natural conditions insofar as it has to be consistent with the world mean of the gas exchange rate, which has been derived from the distribution of bomb radiocarbon in the oceans (K.O. Münnich, and W. Roether, 1967, and M. Stuiver, 1979). A

quadratic relationship between gas exchange rate and wind speed, which is the only one-parametric function among those proposed by the laboratory experiments, has been used in order to check, if the helium-3 exchange rate obtained at 17 m/sec wind speed is consistent with this geochemical mean. For this purpose the gas exchange rate has been corrected for the difference in diffusivities between helium-3 and CO₂ using a square root dependence (B. Jähne and K.O. Münnich, 1979) of the diffusivities (the results do not change significantly if a 2/3 power dependence (B. Jähne and K.O. Münnich, 1979) of the diffusivities is used instead). The gas exchange rate at zero wind speed has been set close to zero as indicated by wind tunnel experiments (D. Flothmann et al., 1979). Frequency distributions of the scalar wind available in the literature (US Navy, Marine Climatic Atlas of the World, Vol. 1 to 6, 1955-1979) have been used for the model calculations. The calculated gas exchange rates agree within $\pm 15\%$ with the geochemical means obtained for the North Atlantic (K.O. Münnich and W. Roether, 1967) and the Atlantic between 40°N and 40°S (M. Stuiver, 1979). The world mean of the CO₂ gas exchange rate has been calculated accordingly to 5.2 m/d.

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